

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
California State University, Los Angeles

MITIGATING MORAL DISTRESS FOR RESUSCITATION TEAM
HEALTHCARE PROVIDERS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

Monique Velasco

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Margaret Brady, PhD, RN, CPNP-PC, Project Chair
Melissa Dyo, PhD, RN, Committee Member

May 2018

ABSTRACT

Healthcare providers who respond to cardiac arrest events often experience the highest form of moral distress. This distress results from the extreme efforts of cardiopulmonary resuscitation and the pronouncement of death. The aim of this 11-week project was to mitigate moral distress for resuscitation team healthcare provider (RTHPs) through education and the introduction of two interventions. A 20-minute education plan was provided to RTHPs in a non-profit, suburban acute care hospital. Education focused on moral distress, the pause (a moment of silence), and the 4 A's to Rise Above Moral Distress self-debriefing tool. The moment of silence initiated at the end of unsuccessful resuscitations was used to acknowledge the life of the deceased and to appreciate the effort of the team. The 4 A's self-debriefing process was accessible through an educational pamphlet on moral distress and the 4 A's outline. A post education survey was distributed to 99 RTHPs. Thirty-nine survey responses were returned with 28 complete surveys analyzed.

Most respondents (89.26%) reported the educational experience helped them talk about morally distressing situations with other healthcare providers. Thirty-seven resuscitation events occurred during the 11 weeks, of which eight were unsuccessful. A moment of silence was implemented in 6 of 8 events (75% utilization). Eighteen of the 29 patients who survived the initial resuscitation did not survive to discharge and 15 moments of silence were performed (83% utilization). The majority of respondents

(96.43%) indicated the moment of silence allowed them to acknowledge the patient's life and their teamwork. The 4 A's debriefing process occurred 86% of the time with 93% of respondents reporting this helped them to acknowledge their own needs in handling moral distress. Based on these responses to the education and resulting changes in procedures, expanded use of the 20-minute education plan is recommended for other nursing departments whose staff experience high levels of moral distress.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
LIST OF TABLES.....	vi
LIST OF FIGURES.....	vii
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS.....	viii
BACKGROUND.....	1
Purpose Statement.....	2
Structural Framework.....	3
Step One.....	3
Step Two.....	4
Step Three.....	4
Step Four.....	5
Step Five.....	5
Step Six.....	6
Step Seven.....	6
REVIEW OF LITERATURE.....	7
Overview.....	7
Moral Distress.....	7
Moral Resilience.....	9
Moral Distress Interventions.....	9
4 A's Process for Identifying and Mitigating Moral Distress.....	11
The Pause.....	12
Summary.....	13
METHODS.....	16
Setting.....	16
Sample.....	16
Ethical Issues.....	17
The Evidence-based Practice Implementation Project Plan.....	18
RESULTS.....	22

DISCUSSION	27
RECOMMENDATIONS	29
REFERENCES	31
APPENDIX A: Iowa Model.....	36
APPENDIX B: IRB Approvals	37
APPENDIX C: Teaching Plan.....	40
APPENDIX D: Qualtrics Survey Questions.....	42

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Sample Demographic Data	23
2. Summary of Thematic Comments from 13 Survey Participants	26

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to express my sincere appreciation to Dr. Margaret Brady for your mentorship through this project. Your expertise, knowledge, and passionate guidance helped to make this project come to fruition. To Dr. Melissa Dyo, I am grateful to have been the recipient of your wisdom and counsel. Your appreciation of healthcare theory and research on moral distress was truly a benefit to my educational experience. To Dr. Penny Weismuller, I am eternally thankful for your uplifting and motivational words of encouragement. I respectfully acknowledge the southern California healthcare team who willingly participated in my quality improvement project, thank you for your unwavering support and dedication. To my parents, Ralph and Annie Espinoza, and my in-laws, Annie Velasco, and the late Gustavo Velasco (1940-2010), my deepest gratitude for fortifying me with the belief that this dream was possible. To my family and friends, for all the times you were magically here to make me laugh, to lift me up, or to push me through, I love you and I am forever grateful.

To my husband Gus, and my children Andre, Nicole, and Dominique, you have been the source of my inspiration, motivation and dedication to achieving this educational goal. My love for you is immense, and I know that being loved by you has been my greatest blessing.

BACKGROUND

The phenomenon of “moral distress” has been described as the painful experience of an ethical dilemma, where healthcare providers are conflicted by structural, professional and personal values in the delivery of patient care (Jameton, 1984; Lachman, 2016). Corley (2002) asserted that the moral concepts of nursing professionals, “commitment, sensitivity, autonomy, sense making, judgement, conflict, competency, and certainty” are affected by morally distressing situations that can arise in healthcare delivery settings (p. 643). In a hallmark, quintessential research study, Hamric & Blackhall (2007) identified that the highest moral distress is realized in circumstances where healthcare providers felt forced to continue aggressive therapies on patients who were actively dying. Healthcare providers who respond to cardiac arrest events often experience the highest form of moral distress that results from the extreme efforts of cardiopulmonary resuscitation and the final pronouncement of death (Hamric & Blackhall, 2007).

The phenomenon of moral distress is identified most frequently in high-intensity nursing units and can contribute to the phenomenon known as “burnout.” Burnout is characterized as feelings of apathy, and emotional, physical and mental exhaustion (Rushton, Batcheller, Schroeder, & Donohue, 2015). High stress work environments, emotional exhaustion, moral distress and burnout have been associated with an increase in healthcare staff disagreements, diminished efficiency, decreased morale, and an increase in nurse turnover (Beumer, 2008). Peer support and debriefing have proven to be effective ways to decrease the amount of moral distress related with ethical challenges during end of life healthcare situations (Edrees et al., 2016). In addition, education of

healthcare providers on caring for the dying, and dealing with the ethical and moral issues that arise in these situations, were demonstrated to decrease levels of moral distress (Rogers, Babgi, & Gomez, 2008). Corley (2002) expressed that education and work place interventions to directly impact morally distressing situations are essential and should be the subject of further research. There is a definite need for hospitals to provide strategies to mitigate moral distress among these at-risk healthcare providers who work in unit specialized teams responding to cardiac arrest events.

Purpose

In the setting for this project, a critical care center in Los Angeles County, the multi-disciplinary healthcare professionals who serve on the resuscitation team did not have access to a formal system for addressing moral distress. In addition, the critical care nurse turnover rate was as high as 10% in the third quarter of 2016. These two issues provided the impetus for the author to identify a strategy to address this situation: therefore, a quality improvement project was initiated. The purpose of this project was to implement post resuscitation debriefing processes to mitigate moral distress among healthcare providers in a 24-bed critical care unit of a non-profit, suburban, acute care hospital. The project intent was threefold: (1) To educate resuscitation team healthcare providers (RTHPs) to identify and acknowledge that moral distress exists in the work environment at the time of a cardiac arrest event; (2) To introduce a 4-step model on identifying and reducing moral distress to assist RTHPs in working through the trauma of cardiac arrest events; and, (3) To provide a silent moment of recognition at the termination of an unsuccessful cardiac resuscitation that allowed the team members to

acknowledge the life of the deceased, and to appreciate the collaborative effort of the healthcare team.

Structural Framework

The process for creating a positive change in a professional healthcare setting requires a blueprint or framework to ensure that the key members of the team are involved. The framework also serves to safeguard that the appropriate steps are taken to continue to progress and maintain the established course (Bonnell & Smith, 2014). The blueprint used for implementation of this evidence-based project was the Iowa Model. According to Doody & Doody (2011), the Iowa Model was originally developed by Titler and her colleagues to promote a process for implementing evidence-based practice and improving healthcare delivery. The Iowa Model was revised in 2015 to improve its clarity and flow (Appendix A) and is widely used to promote excellence in patient care (Bergstrom, 2011).

Step One

According to Doody & Doody (2001), there are seven major steps in the Iowa model needed to implement evidence-based practice into healthcare delivery. The DNP author began by taking the first step in selecting an issue or topic that was identified as requiring an improvement in practice (Doody & Doody, 2011). This step required careful consideration of the significance of the problem, its relevance to practice, and its influence on healthcare delivery. In addition, there had to be a substantial amount of research on the problem to establish buy-in from the multidisciplinary staff. There was one key question that had to be considered in this first step: Was this subject or problem a main concern? If yes, then continue to the next step. If the answer is no, then another

topic should be considered. The staff affirmed that moral distress was a concern. Therefore, the focus of this project was on mitigating moral distress in RTHPs and the proposed strategy to mitigate moral distress was to implement post resuscitation debriefing processes among RTHPs.

Step Two

The second step involved formation of a support team to champion this implementation project (Doody & Doody, 2011). Selecting the right team members was vital to the project's success because the team had to persuade RTHPs to accept the process change. For this reason, the support team consisted of a few resuscitation team members and leadership team partners with a vested interest in the project. The team for this project consisted of the Clinical Director, the charge nurses, the educator, the social worker, the chaplain, and two staff RNs from the Critical Care Unit, as well as, two respiratory therapists. In addition to the support team, initial permission to proceed with the project was approved by the Chief Nursing Officer and the Clinical Director of the Critical Care Unit.

Step Three

The third step was to formulate a body of evidence through database searches utilizing key terms identified by the team and the literature (Doody & Doody, 2011). Performing data searches using trustworthy electronic databases was essential and included: PubMed; CINAHL; Cochrane; QIP, Medline, and University Library resources to find reputable data. A thorough review of the search findings allowed for the selection of a body of evidence that identified the problem and supported the change project.

Step Four

The fourth step was to analyze the quality and reliability of the body of evidence (Doody & Doody, 2011). The team identified that there were adequate research findings that supported the intervention and change process. In the event sufficient evidence was not found to support the project, the team would go back to conduct further research and then return to repeat step 3 to appraise the research.

Step Five

The fifth step was for the team to create a guideline based on the evidence found and to implement a pilot study (Doody & Doody, 2011). A timeframe was set for the process of implementing the change, and the evaluation tools had to be created before the pilot could begin. Careful consideration was taken to address the relevance, benefits, and the feasibility of the process change. The team came to a consensus for the change to occur, and all parties with a vested interest were included in the decision. The evidence-based debriefing tool used for this project was the “4 A’s Model to Rise Above Moral Distress” developed by the American Association of Critical Care Nurses (AACN, 2004). This model presented a framework for nurse leaders to assist their healthcare staff in developing positive changes to mitigate moral distress. The 4 A’s were Ask, Affirm, Assess and Act. The model was used in this project as part of an educational plan to assist healthcare providers to identify their own moral distress. It was used as a guide to aid the resuscitation team members in working toward moral resilience (Savel & Munro, 2015). In conjunction with this debriefing education, the project incorporated a silent moment of recognition at the end of cardiac arrest events. This time out served two purposes. First, it

allowed the team to stop and acknowledge the life of the deceased. Second, it provided the team members the opportunity to acknowledge the collaborative work of the team.

Step Six

The sixth step involves the creation of the standards of care for the hospital based on the successful implementation of the pilot (Doody & Doody, 2011). This step was not part of this project; however, it will be part of future planning. The sixth step requires the team determining whether the evidence-based project was successfully implemented. If the interventions are not successful, the team will consider alternative interventions to address the problem and then return to step five and run another pilot project. If the initial implementation project is a success the team will begin developing policies and procedures to ensure the consistency and quality of the change process. In this phase the team will implement in-service training to healthcare staff to extend the debriefing process to the other units that experience high levels of moral distress.

Step Seven

Step seven is the evaluation of the new standard over time (Doody & Doody, 2011). This step may involve audits or surveys to track the progress of the change. It is important in this phase to identify and correct any elements of the project that did not have a positive outcome. The quality improvement team will be included in this phase, along with the clinical directors and educators of the departments to promote and support the success of the implementation of the debriefing sessions to other units. The Executive Nursing Staff will be informed of the implementation project and results to gain support from the top leadership team. This phase is essential to ensure ongoing success.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

A literature review was performed utilizing research databases in an effort to support the need for this project. The databases searched included: PubMed, PsychInfo, CINAHL, Cochrane Library, and Google Scholar. The following terms were searched: moral distress, moral resilience, critical care nursing, resuscitation team, and interventions to mitigate moral distress. The search was limited to journals published in the English language, peer reviewed, and published between 2012 to present. Additionally, data mining of research articles was used for retrieval of hallmark reference articles. De-duplication was performed to eliminate identical articles identified across the different databases. The results of this literature review are presented below.

Moral Distress

Moral distress was first defined by Andrew Jameton (1984) as “when one knows the right thing to do, but institutional constraints make it nearly impossible to pursue the right course of action” (p.6). Moral distress occurs when healthcare providers are inhibited about providing care for patients in the way they feel is ethically appropriate (Hamric & Blackhall, 2007). Moral distress has been described as the “painful feelings of guilt, frustration, anger and powerlessness” (Henrich et al., 2016, p.57). These feelings commonly arise when nurses are not allowed to provide care they feel is right according to ethical standards, as it threatens the nurses’ integrity (Hamric & Blackhall, 2007; Henrich et al., 2016; Jameton, 1984; Rushton et al., 2015). Critical care nurses have been identified as experiencing the highest levels of moral distress in nursing (Dyo, Kalowes,

& Devries, 2016; Hamric & Blackhall, 2007; Mason et al., 2014; Ozden, Karagozoglu, & Yildirim, 2013).

One of the highest sources of moral distress identified in the literature is end of life care (Browning, 2013; Dodek et al., 2016; Hamric & Blackhall, 2007; Henrich et al., 2016; McAndrew & Leske, 2015; Wiegand & Funk, 2012). Critical care nurses and physicians identify the phenomenon of “futile care” at end of life, as the greatest cause of moral distress in patient care delivery (Browning, 2013; Hamric & Blackhall, 2007; Henrich et al., 2016; Ozden et al., 2013; Wilson, Goettemoeller, Bevan, & McCord, 2013). The advances in healthcare delivery and technology make it possible to live longer and for healthcare providers to deliver life sustaining therapies to patients. Advanced life support technology has resulted in the “extension of life inappropriately, and futile prolonging of patients suffering that has become more commonplace for critical care nurses caring for dying patients” (Browning, 2013, p. 144). Additional sources of moral distress identified in the literature are: conflicts between physicians and nurses; poor communication between physicians and nurses; inadequate communication between physicians and patients; incompetent co-workers; self-incompetence; insufficient resources, lack of appreciation; aggressive care at end of life; and, inadequate pain management (Browning, 2013; Dodek et al., 2016; Dyo et al., 2016; Hamric & Blackhall, 2007; Henrich et al., 2016; Lawrence, 2011; Mason et al., 2014; McAndrew, Leske, & Schroeter, 2016; McAndrew & Leske, 2015; Ozden et al., 2013; Rushton et al., 2015; Sauerland, Marotta, Peinemann, Berndt, & Robichaux, 2014; Wiegand & Funk, 2012; Wilson et al., 2013). This long list of moral distress sources that has been identified as affecting healthcare providers in a high-intensity work setting was strong evidence that a

need for the development of interventions and prevention strategies was essential (Lachman, 2016).

Moral Resilience

Moral resilience was defined as, “the capacity of an individual to sustain or restore their integrity in response to moral complexity, confusion, distress or setbacks” (Rushton, 2016, p. 112). According to Rushton, Batcheller, Schroeder, and Donohue (2015), nurses who develop higher resilience have a strong ability to protect themselves from emotional exhaustion and a high capacity for resilience may help to foster personal accomplishment. A healthcare provider who has established moral resilience has developed a level of confidence and established coping skills that can be used to diminish morally distressing situations (Rushton et al., 2015). Moral resilience is built over time and experience. It can be nurtured by an ethical work environment and leadership that encourage discussion of difficult ethical situations in a safe, non-judgmental environment (Lachman, 2016; Rushton, 2016). Moral courage was defined as “the willingness to speak out and do that which is right in the face of forces that would lead a person to act in some other way” (Lachman, 2007, p.131). Healthcare providers who, in the face of adversity, have advocated for the rights of their patients have exhibited moral courage (Sauerland et al., 2014; Wiegand & Funk, 2012). Fostering moral resilience may provide healthcare providers with the skills and determination to carry-out acts of moral courage (Lachman, 2016).

Moral Distress Interventions

In the literature, there was a lack of robust studies analyzing the efficacy of moral distress interventions. However, there was literature that was based on supportive

services and debriefing techniques which have assisted healthcare providers with developing moral and ethical skills and resilience (Edrees et al., 2016; Gordon, Ridley, Boston, & Dahl, 2012; McCue, 2010; Rushton et al., 2015; Santiago & Abdool, 2011). The Browning (2013) study queried nurses who had attended end of life patient care conferences and training and they were found to have increased psychological empowerment. The study identified that nurses who had reported strong psychological empowerment also reported lower moral distress intensity and less frequency of morally distressing situations. That finding correlated with an increased knowledge and understanding of moral and ethical issues (Browning, 2013).

Gordon, Ridley, Boston, and Dahl (2012) offered an 8-hour educational conference to promote awareness of moral distress and end of life care for all intensive care unit staff employed in a Toronto hospital. The conference was offered twelve times to ensure all intensive care multidisciplinary staff were provided the education. The conference was designed with the hope of accomplishing two goals: to build relations among the multidisciplinary ICU team members; and to build awareness of how other disciplines perceive and experience moral distress. The conference provided an opportunity for open dialogue on morally distressing issues including end of life care. The staff received additional resources and access to a call-in line to discuss moral and ethical issues without fear of repercussions. The conference received a high satisfaction rating from the attendees (92%). However, there were no validation tools utilized to measure the overall efficacy of the educational conferences (Gordon et al., 2012).

Santiago and Abdool (2011) utilized debriefing discussions focusing on ethics to mitigate moral distress. Debriefing sessions were held monthly and after critical incident

situations to encourage sharing of experiences and opportunities for learning in a non-punitive setting. The sessions were administered by a bio-ethicist and supported by the hospital's clinical leader. The results of the debriefing sessions promoted awareness, provided solutions to ethical situations that arise in healthcare delivery, and resulted in the development of cohesive interdisciplinary strategies for family meetings and complex situations (Santiago & Abdool, 2011).

Edrees et al. (2016) implemented a telephone support program to assist healthcare staff who experienced an adverse event and were experiencing emotional stress. The program was called "the RISE (Resilience in Stressful Events)," and the calls to this program were handled by peers with training in RAPID-PFA, an assessment and debriefing process that was designed to manage situations involving emotional distress (Edrees et al., 2016). Although the individuals who called were positive about the experience, the study call center only received a limited number of callers. Thus, the program did not achieve the success expected due to a lack of nurses accessing the resource (Edrees et al., 2016).

4 A's Process for Identifying and Mitigating Moral Distress

The AACN (2004) developed the 4 A's Model to Rise Above Moral Distress to provide a process that healthcare providers can use to identify, address and work through morally distressing situations. McCue (2010) utilized this framework in a situation that involved a nurse executive who was asked to take a course of action against an impaired nurse by a Chief Executive Officer (CEO). The nurse executive was asked by the CEO to terminate the impaired nurse, however, the nurse executive believed this was inappropriate and went against her ethical responsibility to assist the impaired nurse

(McCue, 2010). In this case study, McCue (2010) identified the 4 A's: Ask, Affirm, Assess, and Act that the nurse executive utilized to work through this morally distressing situation. In the ask and affirm steps, the nurse executive acknowledged that she was experiencing moral distress and identified her ethical responsibility in the situation (McCue, 2010). In the assess and act steps, the nurse executive evaluated the potential consequences of going against the CEO's request to terminate the impaired nurse, and ultimately acted by discussing with the CEO the ethical responsibilities of the hospital to assist the impaired nurse in seeking help for her impairment (McCue, 2010). Although this tool was used by agencies, there were no articles that substantiated the efficacy of its implementation.

The Pause

Bartels (2014) developed "the Pause" after experiencing a death in the emergency department where a pastor asked the members of the care team to stay for a moment of silence while he prayed over the patient. The moment of silence allowed Mr. Bartels, an emergency room registered nurse, a time to reflect on the life of the patient who had just passed. At that moment, Mr. Bartels realized that he had been so busy providing care, that he forgot the patient in the bed was a person who had a life and a family (Bartels, 2014). In busy, high acuity, fast-paced patient care settings, healthcare providers may get busy completing tasks and care functions and forget to acknowledge that the patient is a person. Bartels (2014) felt compelled to use his experience to benefit other healthcare providers and initiated a one minute pause after an unsuccessful resuscitation event. The practice took hold, as the staff came to appreciate the opportunity to personally

acknowledge their feelings and emotions after a stressful, unrewarded event (Bartels, 2014).

The Pause has spread due in part to a keynote speech delivered at a nursing conference by Dorrie Fontaine, dean of the University of Virginia School of Nursing where she discussed the success of Mr. Bartels' intervention (Bartels, 2014). Copeland (2016) used the Pause as part of an intervention to address the trauma experienced by healthcare providers who had been a part of a resuscitation event in a busy emergency department setting. The goal, according to Copeland (2016), was to establish a moment for the healthcare responders to acknowledge the patient and to initiate a process to debrief and allow time for the primary care nurses to collect themselves before returning to the busy patient care environment of the emergency department. The Pause was the first part of the intervention for this study followed by a short seven question debriefing used to openly discuss what went well, opportunities for improvement, and to offer support to family and team members (Copeland, 2016). The study was evaluated by the participants using pre, mid, and post surveys and was determined an overall success as the responders reported improvement in the feeling supported categories (Copeland, 2016).

Summary

In summary, moral distress has clearly been identified as a phenomenon that is experienced by healthcare providers who work in high intensity work settings involving end of life care (Henrich et al., 2016; McAndrew & Leske, 2015). There was limited research on interventions and possible strategies to address and mitigate moral distress; however, debriefing was identified to assist healthcare providers in acknowledging moral

distress, and promoting moral resilience (Copeland, 2016; McCue, 2010; Santiago & Abdool, 2011).

The 4 A's: Ask, Affirm, Assess and Act was a reflective, debriefing guide developed by AACN to assist healthcare providers in working through morally distressing situations (Rushton, 2006). The tool was designed for nurses to use as a process to analyze a distressing situation they are experiencing and to take the appropriate steps to work through the situation (McCue, 2010; Rushton, 2006). The first step in the reflective debriefing tool was to ask if the distress was the result of a moral or ethical conflict (McCue, 2010; Rushton, 2006). The second step was to affirm the moral distress was real and to recognize the need to address the situation. Additionally, the healthcare provider in this situation must acknowledge their professional responsibility to help themselves (McCue, 2010; Rushton, 2006). The third step involved assessing the situation to determine if the healthcare provider was prepared to make an effective change (Rushton, 2006). This step required the healthcare provider to look at the morally distressing situation from the perspective of the patient, family, healthcare provider and the overall possibility that an action would result in a positive change (Rushton, 2006). The final step was to act. In this step, Rushton (2006) described healthcare providers as advocates for change, poised to take-action to ensure the health and welfare of their patients and themselves. The healthcare providers must be prepared to have their actions accepted or rejected. And, they should have a healthy process in place for caring for themselves with either result. The 4 A's was developed by AACN (2004) to assist nurses to work through moral distress through a reflective self-debriefing process, however, it

has been utilized as a guide for healthcare leaders to assist their staff in identifying and mitigating moral distress (McCue, 2010; Rushton, 2006).

Bartels (2014) developed “The Pause” to allow the resuscitation team to acknowledge the life of a patient who has passed after an unsuccessful cardiopulmonary resuscitation and to recognize the combined work of the team. The importance of utilizing this process as part of a method for mitigating moral distress was to give time for the team to come down from the rush of the tasks and to allow an opportunity for the RTHPs to feel the emotion. Recognizing the feelings that arise from morally distressing end of life situations was an important step in the process of addressing this serious problem (Copeland, 2016; Rushton et al., 2015).

It was the author’s hope this EBP implementation project, with the use of the 4 A’s and the Pause, would assist RTHPs in identifying, acknowledging and developing the skills to work through morally distressing situations and to begin to acquire moral resilience. Moral resilience was the ability to respond to morally distressing situations without succumbing to the stress, and it can be encouraged in healthcare providers by fostering hope (Rushton et al., 2015).

METHODS

This section describes the steps that were taken to implement post resuscitation debriefing to assist RTHPs to identify and mitigate moral distress associated with an unsuccessful cardiopulmonary resuscitation. First, the setting for the project, the inclusion criteria for the sample of study participants, and a description of the study design are explained. Second, the steps that were taken to ensure that ethical issues associated with the project were appropriately addressed are described. Third, the process that was used for evaluating this project is delineated. And, lastly, the method of data analysis is explained.

Setting

This evidence-based practice (EBP) implementation project took place at a non-profit, suburban, community hospital located in Southern California. It involved the multidisciplinary resuscitation healthcare team and took place at the location of an unsuccessful cardiopulmonary resuscitation event. The location was a 548-bed licensed acute care hospital that is a Certified Stroke and ST elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) receiving center. The hospital averaged 206 cardiopulmonary resuscitation events per year and approximately 17 cardiopulmonary resuscitations per month.

Sample

The sample for this project included healthcare providers who were part of a multidisciplinary resuscitation team (i.e., nurses, respiratory therapists, emergency medical technicians, physicians, pharmacists, social workers, and chaplains). Inclusion criteria required that the team member responded to code blue calls that involved unsuccessful resuscitative efforts at the project hospital. All members of the team were

invited to participate in the Pause, which was referred to as the Moment of Silence for this project, and 4 A's at the end of an unsuccessful resuscitation event and the follow-up survey. Participation was completely voluntary. There was no incentive offered for participation and no repercussions for non-participation.

Ethical Issues

Approval for this translation of evidence into practice project was requested from the Chief Nursing Officer of the project facility and the Clinical Director of the critical care unit. An application was submitted to the Institutional Review Board at California State University Long Beach for this evidence-based implementation project. This project involved an introduction of change processes for healthcare providers only, and did not involve any patient information, patient demographics, or patient care change.

Accordingly, an expedited review was granted and the project was IRB approved. The RTHPs were given the option of voluntary participation in the Moment of Silence immediately following the calling of an unsuccessful resuscitation and just prior to the initiation of the silent recognition. The healthcare provider was free to decide, without repercussions for choosing not to participate, and did not receive any type of reward for participation.

The option to opt-out of participation in this project was provided for each participant and followed the guidelines set by the California State University Long Beach Institutional Review Board. The RTHPs were provided with at minimum the following: (1) Detailed information was given about the projects purpose and what RTHPs would be asked to do as participants in this study; (2) The risks and benefits, if any, of the project were thoroughly described; (3) All participants had the right to terminate their

involvement in the project at any time during the study; and, (4) Information about the members of the project team conducting the evidence-based implementation project was provided.

Implementation Steps of the Iowa Model

This translation of evidence into practice project used a modified blueprint of the Iowa Model, originally developed by Titler and colleagues (Doody & Doody, 2011). The first two phases of the Iowa model were to identify a relevant subject and establish a support team to champion the evidence-based practice (EBP) project (Doody & Doody, 2011). The aim of this project, as previously stated, was to implement a post resuscitation team debriefing process to mitigate moral distress. The hospital based champion team included the following members from the Critical Care Center: The clinical director; the charge nurses; the educator; the social worker; the chaplain; two staff registered nurses; and two respiratory therapists. This team assisted in championing the project during the initiation and implementation phases of the EBP project. To establish buy-in from this support team, a futile care resuscitation scenario that frequently occurred in this hospital setting and clearly described moral dilemmas associated with these healthcare delivery situations were reviewed.

The third and fourth phases in the Iowa model (2015) blueprint was a review of literature and analysis of the research to ensure it adequately supported the change method that was selected (Doody & Doody, 2011). In this EBP implementation project, debriefing had been identified to assist healthcare providers in mitigating moral distress (Copeland, 2016; McCue, 2010; Santiago & Abdool, 2011).

The fifth phase was to create a guideline for the implementation of the change process (Doody & Doody, 2011). This project utilized the 4 A's to Rise Above Moral Distress, a debriefing tool framework, to educate and assist RTHPs in working through the situations that cause moral distress (Rushton, 2006). In addition to the debriefing education, a voluntary 30-second moment of silence was conducted at the end of unsuccessful cardiac resuscitation events. This afforded the RTHPs time to acknowledge the life of the deceased patient, and a moment to recognize the united work of the resuscitation team. The moment of silence only occurred at the end of unsuccessful resuscitation events as the RTHPs in successful resuscitations dedicated their time to the continuation of care of the resuscitated patient.

The education process for the RTHPs included the definition of moral distress, the 4 A's to Rise Above Moral Distress (AACN, 2004) and the Moment of Silence through in-services provided during scheduled mandatory staff meetings over a period of 3 weeks. A 20-minute power point presentation covered the 4 A's: Ask, Affirm, Assess, and Act debriefing process, and the Moment of Silence process. The 4 A's education included the following: (1) Ask: The RTHPs must ask themselves if the feelings of unease or distress they were experiencing were the result of moral or ethical issues (AACN, 2004); (2) Affirm: The RTHPs needed to affirm the experience of moral distress and to acknowledge their professional responsibility to address the situation (AACN, 2004); (3) Assess: The RTHPs assessed and analyzed the risks of doing what they believed was the morally right thing to do (AACN, 2004); and, (4) Act: The RTHPs had to take-action and address the morally distressing concerns to preserve the integrity of their moral character (AACN, 2004). The staff were engaged in the lecture through imagery and mindfulness

teaching strategies to support understanding of moral distress. And, questioning was used to promote open discussion of morally distressing situations. A pamphlet was provided to the RTHPs to accompany the power point presentation and included the 4 A's debriefing process, the Moment of Silence process, and resources available from the hospital site for RTHPs to access for further information and assistance in managing moral distress. The information was posted on the critical care unit's share point electronic platform to provide the staff with around the clock access to the education and resources available.

The three components: The 4 A's, Moment of Silence, and the educational program were evaluated using an electronic survey sent out through the California State University Qualtrics survey program. The Likert scale survey was made available through staff email to RTHPs who had been involved in the project. Survey responses remained anonymous. The survey included questions relating to identifying and mitigating moral distress post implementation of the 11-week EBP project and included the Likert scale questions listed in Appendix C. The survey was used to assess if the goals of the interventions were met. The rate of utilization was used to determine the value of the interventions. The feasibility of the project was determined based on receptiveness to the project and the number of staff who participated in the study. Descriptive Statistics were used to describe the participants and the data listed. The results of the survey were evaluated using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSSTM) Version 24 electronic software.

The Iowa model (2015) has two additional phases that include the creation of new standards of care based on the success of the implementation project and evaluation of the new standards over time (Doody & Doody, 2011). These two phases were not

included in the initial EBP implementation process. However, they may be addressed after the conclusion of this DNP project. This project concluded with an evaluation of the implementation project utilizing a Likert scale survey.

RESULTS

The project focused on mitigating moral distress associated with unsuccessful resuscitation events through implementation of an education plan and two interventions. The implementation of the two interventions was performed from October 1, 2017 through December 21, 2017. At the culmination of the implementation period a survey was used to measure how the teaching plan and interventions were received.

The survey was distributed via email on December 22, 2017 to 99 healthcare providers who were all members of the resuscitation team. The total respondents to the survey numbered thirty-nine (39) with an attrition rate of 60.6%. Eleven (11) responses had missing answers, thus twenty-eight (28) complete survey responses were used for data analysis. The demographic characteristics of the participants is summarized in Table 1. The respondents were primarily female (78.57%), White or White - Hispanic (64.29%), and the predominant age range was between 25 – 44 years of age (71.43%). The majority of survey responses were from registered nurses (71.43%), and the reported level of education was a bachelor's degree or above (67.86%). The highest number of survey responses (32.14%) reported 5 years or less of healthcare experience, and (75%) reported 15 years or less of healthcare experience.

Table 1

Sample Demographic Data

Sample Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
18-24	1	3.57%
25-34	11	39.29%
35-44	9	32.14%
45-54	2	7.14%
55-64	4	14.29%
65-74	1	3.57%
75 or more	0	0%
Gender		
Female	22	78.57%
Male	6	21.40%
Ethnicity		
American Indian or Alaska Native	0	0%
Asian	5	17.86%
Black or African American	1	3.57%
Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander	1	3.57%
White (Hispanic)	7	25.00%
White (Non-Hispanic)	11	39.29%
Other	3	10.71%
Occupation		
Physician	0	0%
Registered Nurse	20	71.43%
Respiratory Therapist	5	17.86%
Pharmacist	0	0%
Social Worker	0	0%
Chaplain	3	10.71%
Medical Technician	0	0%
Years of Experience		
0-5	9	32.14%
6-10	6	21.43%
11-15	6	21.43%
16-20	1	3.57%
21-25	0	0%
26-30	2	7.14%
31 or more	4	14.29%
Education		
High School Diploma	0	0%
Associates degree	9	32.14%
Bachelors' degree	10	35.71%
Masters' degree	8	28.57%
Doctorate degree	1	3.57%
Post-doctoral studies	0	0%

Note. $N = 28$

The first area of focus was to find out if education on moral distress would provide RTHPs with a basic understanding and a level of comfort for them to talk about moral distress with other healthcare providers. The author posed the first question: Rate the extent you felt the moral distress education helped you to understand what moral distress is? Out of the twenty-eight responses, twenty-six (92.86%) “strongly agreed” or “agreed” that the education helped their understanding of moral distress. The second question on education was: How useful was the education in assisting you to feel more comfortable in talking about moral distress with other healthcare providers. Twenty-five (89.29%) reported that the education was “moderately helpful” to “extremely helpful”.

The second area of focus was on the moment of silence initiated at the end of unsuccessful resuscitations. There was a total of thirty-seven (37) code blue events during the project implementation and eight (8) unsuccessful resuscitations. Six out of the eight unsuccessful resuscitations were followed by a moment of silence for a rate of utilization of 75 %. The first question relating to the moment of silence was: Rate the extent you felt the moment of silence allowed you to personally acknowledge the life of the patient. The second question was: Rate the extent you felt the moment of silence allowed you to personally acknowledge the work of the team. The response for both questions was that 96.42% “strongly agreed” or “agreed”. The third question was: How valuable would you rate the moment of silence? Twenty-two (22) respondents chose “excellent” (78.57%), and an additional three (3) responded “good” (10.71%). The fourth question was: Would you recommend continuing the use of the moment of silence? Twenty-two (22) responded “definitely yes” (78.57%), and an additional five (5) responses were “probably yes” (17.86%).

There was one major unanticipated outcome of the project. There were twenty-nine (29) patients who survived the initial resuscitation; and of those, eighteen (18) did not survive to discharge. Fifteen (15) moments of silence were performed after the expiration of those patients for a rate of utilization of 83.33%. Subsequent to the first resuscitation event, these 15 patients were given a “do not resuscitate” status. They passed away in the critical care unit; however, the care providers utilized the moment of silence with the RTHPs and family at the bedside. The use of the moment of silence on those patients was a decision made by the RTHPs with the family.

The third area of focus was on the use of the debriefing component of the 4 A’s. The first question was: Rate the extent you felt the 4 A’s helped you to acknowledge your own needs in handling moral distress. Fourteen respondents (50%) “strongly agreed”, and an additional twelve respondents “agreed” (42.86%). The second question was: How often did you use the 4 A’s as a debriefing process after a resuscitation? Twenty-five (25) respondents reported attending a total of forty-four (44) resuscitation events and utilized the 4 A’s debriefing tool thirty-eight (38) times for a rate of utilization of 86.36%. Twenty-two (22) of the twenty-five (25) respondents reported using the 4 A’s debriefing process at least one time or more (88%).

The survey offered two open-ended questions that were reviewed by the author to discern any themes found in the responses. There were thirteen responses to the question: For those who participated in a moment of silence, do you have any comments you wish to share about this personal experience, or suggestions you wish to share about the process? The thematic responses are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2

Summary of Thematic Comments from 13 Survey Participants

Moment of Silence

Respect and Dignity

Aids in seeing the expired patient as a human being rather than just an object that now needs to be forgotten.

Allows us to acknowledge a life and the efforts we put in to saving it.

It allows us to show respect for the individual and closure for the family.

Staff and Family Closure

It not only helped the staff, but also the family.

I was able to look around the room and recognize all the effort and work we put into caring for this patient.

Very good in helping staff deal with end of life.

I appreciated the opportunity to acknowledge all our efforts.

It allows us to recognize those that come to assist in the efforts.

DISCUSSION

The aim of this study was to mitigate moral distress for RTHPs that was associated with unsuccessful resuscitation events. Through the process of the revised Iowa model, the RTHPs were provided with education on moral distress and introduced to two interventions: the moment of silence and the 4 A's to Rise Above Moral Distress debriefing tool. The overall success of this project is the receptiveness of the RTHPs to use the education and interventions to talk about and work through morally distressing situations. Based on the post implementation survey responses, the education was well received with 92.86% of respondents agreeing the education helped them to understand moral distress, and 89.29% noting the educational experience helped them to talk about morally distressing situations with other healthcare providers. The positive response to the education on moral distress in end of life situations is promising as it has been shown to decrease levels of moral distress (Rogers, Babgi, & Gomez, 2008).

The moment of silence intervention introduced at the end of unsuccessful resuscitation events and the 4 A's individual debriefing tool was positively received. Most survey respondents (96.43%) reported the moment of silence allowed them to acknowledge the life of the patient and the work of the team. And, 92.86% of respondents indicated the 4 A's to Rise Above Moral Distress helped them to acknowledge their own needs in handling moral distress. This level of positive response is encouraging as debriefing and peer support have been successful in lowering moral and ethical distress associated with end of life situations (Edrees et al., 2016).

This project had limitations beginning with implementation of the project at a single hospital location and a small sample size. The number of unsuccessful

resuscitation events was low during the project implementation limiting the opportunities for the interventions to be utilized. There was no baseline survey data performed prior to implementation of the project; thus, post-survey results were not measured against pre-intervention data. Survey responses were not received from all disciplines of the RTHPs limiting the study findings to three out of seven disciplines involved in resuscitative events. The author acknowledges that there were 60 members of the resuscitation team that received and did not respond to the survey. There was no tracking of healthcare participants involved in the resuscitation events to ensure the anonymity of the survey responses. There may have been several reasons why these team members did not respond. They may not have participated in an unsuccessful resuscitation due to the low number of occurrences. They may not have read their e-mail, wished to provide their opinion, and or wanted to spend the time completing the survey. Additionally, they may have had concerns about anonymity.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The initial recommendation would be the dissemination of the project results to the RTHPs, the directors of the critical care center and the nursing executive team at the project implementation site. This would provide an opportunity to obtain buy-in for further implementation of the interventions to other healthcare delivery departments. The recommendation for practice would be to continue the dissemination of education and interventions to other nursing units that have difficult end of life care situations. The education would have to be modified to the unique moral and ethical situations that arise in each nursing unit. The introduction of this process in other units should begin with a pre-project survey to measure the levels of moral distress of the healthcare team. This would provide baseline data that the author could use to measure the effectiveness of the education and interventions introduced in the project.

The revised Iowa models sixth step in implementation of research into practice is the creation of the standards of care for the hospital based on the successful implementation of the pilot project (Doody & Doody, 2011). The recommendation based on the positive response to the education and interventions would be the development of policies and procedures to safeguard the dependability of the new process. Additionally, implementation of in-service training to healthcare staff on moral distress, the moment of silence and the 4 A's debriefing process should be extended to other units that experience high levels of moral distress.

The last step of the Iowa model is the evaluation of the new standard over time (Doody & Doody, 2011). The recommendation would be to create an audit tool to track the progress of the change. The audit would provide the information necessary to make

modifications and adjustments to ensure the process change remains consistent with the goals of the project. The clinical directors and educators would be instrumental in establishing what departments the project should be utilized. The quality improvement team should be included to assist with the development of the audit tool and with the overall process of evaluation over time.

REFERENCES

- American Association of Critical Care Nurses (AACN). The 4 A's to rise above moral distress toolkit. Aliso Viejo, CA: AACN, 2004.
- Bartels, J. B. (2014). The pause. *Critical Care Nurse*, 34(1), 74-75.
doi:10.4037/ccn2014962
- Bergstrom, K. (2011). Development of a radiation skin care protocol and algorithm using the Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice. *Clinical Journal Oncology Nursing*, 15(6), 593-595a. doi:10.1188/11.CJON.593-595
- Beumer, C. M. (2008). Innovative solutions: The effect of a workshop on reducing the experience of moral distress in an intensive care unit setting. *Dimensions in Critical Care Nursing*, 27(6), 263-267.
doi:10.1097/01.DCC.0000338871.77658.03
- Bonnel, W. E., & Smith, K. V. (2014). *Proposal writing for nursing capstones and clinical projects*. New York: Springer.
- Browning, A. M. (2013). CNE article: Moral distress and psychological empowerment in critical care nurses caring for adults at end of life. *American Journal of Critical Care*, 22(2), 143-151. doi:10.4037/ajcc2013437
- Copeland, D. (2016). Implementation of a Post-Code Pause. *Journal of Trauma Nursing*, 23(2), 58-64. doi:10.1097/JTN.0000000000000187
- Corley, M. C. (2002). Nurse moral distress: A proposed theory and research agenda. *Nursing Ethics*, 9(6), 636-650. doi:10.1191/0969733002ne557oa

- Dodek, P. M., Wong, H., Norena, M., Ayas, N., Reynolds, S. C., Keenan, S. P., . . . Alden, L. (2016). Moral distress in intensive care unit professionals is associated with profession, age, and years of experience. *Journal of Critical Care, 31*(1), 178-182. doi:10.1016/j.jcrc.2015.10.011
- Doody, C. M., & Doody, O. (2011). Introducing evidence into nursing practice: Using the IOWA model. *British Journal of Nursing, 20*(11), 661-664. doi:10.12968/bjon.2011.20.11.661
- Dyo, M., Kalowes, P., & Devries, J. (2016). Moral distress and intention to leave: A comparison of adult and paediatric nurses by hospital setting. *Intensive & Critical Care Nursing, 36*, 42-48. doi:10.1016/j.iccn.2016.04.003
- Edrees, H., Connors, C., Paine, L., Norvell, M., Taylor, H., & Wu, A. W. (2016). Implementing the RISE second victim support programme at the Johns Hopkins Hospital: A case study. *BMJ Open, 6*(9), e011708. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2016-011708
- Gordon, E., Ridley, B., Boston, J., & Dahl, E. (2012). The building bridges initiative: learning with, from and about to create an interprofessional end-of-life program. *Dynamics, 23*(4), 37-41.
- Hamric, A. B., & Blackhall, L. J. (2007). Nurse-physician perspectives on the care of dying patients in intensive care units: Collaboration, moral distress, and ethical climate. *Critical Care Medicine, 35*(2), 422-429. doi:10.1097/01.CCM.0000254722.50608.2D

- Henrich, N. J., Dodek, P. M., Alden, L., Keenan, S. P., Reynolds, S., & Rodney, P. (2016). Causes of moral distress in the intensive care unit: A qualitative study. *Journal of Critical Care, 35*, 57-62. doi:10.1016/j.jcrc.2016.04.033
- Jameton, A. (1984). *Nursing practice: The ethical issues*. Englewood Cliffs, N.J.: Prentice-Hall.
- Lachman, V. D. (2016). Ethics, Law, and Policy. Moral Resilience: Managing and Preventing Moral Distress and Moral Residue. *MEDSURG Nursing, 25*(2), 121-124.
- Lawrence, L. A. (2011). Work engagement, moral distress, education level, and critical reflective practice in intensive care nurses. *Nursing Forum, 46*(4), 256-268. doi:10.1111/j.1744-6198.2011.00237.x
- Mason, V. M., Leslie, G., Clark, K., Lyons, P., Walke, E., Butler, C., & Griffin, M. (2014). Compassion fatigue, moral distress, and work engagement in surgical intensive care unit trauma nurses: a pilot study. *Dimensions of Critical Care Nursing : DCCN, 33*(4), 215-225. doi:10.1097/DCC.0000000000000056
- McAndrew, N. S., Leske, J., & Schroeter, K. (2016). Moral distress in critical care nursing: The state of the science. *Nursing Ethics*. doi:10.1177/0969733016664975
- McAndrew, N. S., & Leske, J. S. (2015). A balancing act: Experiences of nurses and physicians when making end-of-life decisions in intensive care units. *Clinical Nursing Research, 24*(4), 357-374. doi:10.1177/1054773814533791
- McCue, C. (2010). Using the AACN framework to alleviate moral distress. *Online Journal of Issues in Nursing, 16*(1), 9. doi:10.3912/OJIN.Vol16No01PPT02

- Ozden, D., Karagozoglu, S., & Yildirim, G. (2013). Intensive care nurses' perception of futility: Job satisfaction and burnout dimensions. *Nursing Ethics, 20*(4), 436-447. doi:10.1177/0969733012466002
- Rogers, S., Babgi, A., & Gomez, C. (2008). Educational interventions in end-of-life care: Part I: An educational intervention responding to the moral distress of NICU nurses provided by an ethics consultation team. *Advanced Neonatal Care, 8*(1), 56-65. doi:10.1097/01.ANC.0000311017.02005.20
- Rushton, C. H. (2006). Defining and addressing moral distress: Tools for critical care nursing leaders. *AACN Advanced Critical Care, 17*(2), 161-168.
- Rushton, C. H. (2016). Moral resilience: A capacity for navigating moral distress in critical care. *AACN Advanced Critical Care, 27*(1), 111-119. doi:10.4037/aacnacc2016275
- Rushton, C. H., Batcheller, J., Schroeder, K., & Donohue, P. (2015). Burnout and resilience among nurses practicing in high-intensity settings. *American Journal of Critical Care, 24*(5), 412-420. doi:10.4037/ajcc2015291
- Santiago, C., & Abdool, S. (2011). Conversations about challenging end-of-life cases: Ethics debriefing in the medical surgical intensive care unit. *Dynamics, 22*(4), 26-30.
- Sauerland, J., Marotta, K., Peinemann, M. A., Berndt, A., & Robichaux, C. (2014). Assessing and addressing moral distress and ethical climate, part 1. *Dimensions of Critical Care Nursing, 33*(4), 234-245. doi:10.1097/DCC.0000000000000050
- Savel, R. H., & Munro, C. L. (2015). Moral distress, moral courage. *American Journal of Critical Care, 24*(4), 276-278. doi:10.4037/ajcc2015738

Wiegand, D. L., & Funk, M. (2012). Consequences of clinical situations that cause critical care nurses to experience moral distress. *Nursing Ethics, 19*(4), 479-487.

doi:10.1177/0969733011429342

Wilson, M. A., Goettemoeller, D. M., Bevan, N. A., & McCord, J. M. (2013). Moral distress: Levels, coping and preferred interventions in critical care and transitional care nurses. *Journal of Clinical Nursing, 22*(9/10), 1455-1466.

doi:10.1111/jocn.12128

APPENDIX A
THE IOWA MODEL (2015)

The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care

Used/Reprinted with permission from the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics. Copyright 2015.

APPENDIX B
CSULB IRB APPROVAL

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LONG BEACH
OFFICE OF RESEARCH & SPONSORED PROGRAMS

DATE: September 28, 2017

TO: Monique Velasco, MSN
FROM: CSULB IRB

PROJECT TITLE: [1132775-1] Mitigating Moral Distress
REFERENCE #: 18-094
SUBMISSION TYPE: New Project

ACTION: ACKNOWLEDGED
EFFECTIVE DATE: September 28, 2017

Thank you for submitting the New Quality Improvement Nursing Project materials. The California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board has ACKNOWLEDGED your submission. No further action on submission 1132775-1 is required at this time because the CSULB IRB determined this project qualifies for IRB Exempt status according to the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services (DHHS) regulations at 45 CFR 46.101 (b)(1).

The following items are acknowledged in this submission:

- Advertisement - Appendix E - MMD Pamphlet.docx (UPDATED: 09/22/2017)
- Application Form - MVelasco -2016 CSULB IRB 92217 rev.doc (UPDATED: 09/22/2017)
- Letter - Appendix G - Mitigating Moral Distress.docx (UPDATED: 09/22/2017)
- Letter - Appendix F - Mitigating Moral Distress .docx (UPDATED: 09/22/2017)
- Letter - Appendix A - Mitigating Moral Distress.docx (UPDATED: 09/22/2017)
- Other - Appendix D - MMD PPP.docx (UPDATED: 09/22/2017)
- Other - Appendix B - Mitigating Moral Distress.docx (UPDATED: 09/22/2017)
- Questionnaire/Survey - Appendix C - Qualtrics Survey.docx (UPDATED: 09/22/2017)

If you have any questions, please contact the CSULB IRB at (562) 985-5314 or IRB@csulb.edu. Please include your project title and reference number in all correspondence with this committee.

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LONG BEACH

SCHOOL OF NURSING

Faculty Supervisor's Statement

Date: August 6, 2017

TO: CSULB Institutional Review Board for the Protection of Human Subjects

FROM: Margaret Brady, PhD, RN, CPNP-PC *margaret brady*
 Faculty Supervisor:
 Professor, CSULB School of Nursing
 Cell 714-325-9276
 Nursing 562-985-8248

NAME OF STUDENT: **Monique Velasco**

TITLE OF PROJECT: Mitigating Moral Distress of Resuscitation Team Health Care Providers

SPONSOR'S STATEMENT:

As Ms. Velasco's faculty chair for her Doctor of Nursing Practice project, I will be supervising her quality improvement study at her workplace. Ms. Velasco's quality improvement project involves the implementation of a post resuscitation debriefing processes to mitigate moral distress among healthcare providers (HCPs) in a critical care unit at her work setting. The project intent is threefold: (1) To educate HCPs to identify and acknowledge that moral distress exists in the work environment at the time of a cardiac arrest event; (2) To introduce a 4-step model for identifying and reducing moral distress to assist HCPs in working through the trauma of cardiac arrest events; and, (3) To provide a silent moment of recognition at the termination of an unsuccessful cardiac resuscitation that allows team members to acknowledge the life of the deceased, and to appreciate the collaborative effort of the healthcare team.

Data collection for this project consists of a follow-up electronic survey sent to HCPs who voluntarily agreed to participate in the moment of silence project and participated in resuscitation efforts at the hospital project site that occurred during the designated study timeframe. The link to the electronic survey is included in Ms. Velasco's IRB application. Completion of the survey is voluntary as noted in opt-out statement on the initial section of the survey. The survey focuses on the HCPs' evaluation of the moment of silence and the 4 A's as a strategy to reduce moral distress and promote team communication.

Data from this study will be destroyed according to IRB standards after completion of analysis. I will ensure Ms. Velasco adheres to all aspects of human subject protection identified by the IRB. My signature below certifies that I as Faculty Sponsor of this research have read and approve the attached application. An agency approval letter is enclosed with her IRB application.

To: The California State University, Long Beach
Institutional Review Board

From: [REDACTED]

Re: Monique Velasco, MSN, RN
Doctor of Nursing Capstone Evidence Based Implementation Project

Ms. Velasco and I have met and discussed her proposed Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) evidence based implementation project to mitigate moral distress for resuscitation team healthcare providers. This project will implement two interventions. The first intervention is "The Pause" developed by Jonathon Bartels at the University of Virginia. It will be referred to as "A moment of silence" that will be conducted for 30 seconds at the end of unsuccessful cardiopulmonary resuscitations. The "moment of silence" will allow the resuscitation team to honor the life of the patient that has passed and to acknowledge the efforts of the team. The second intervention is the use of AACN's 4-A's debriefing tool to assist resuscitation staff members to identify and reduce moral distress associated with unsuccessful cardiopulmonary arrest events.

I am in agreement with Ms. Velasco conducting a staff in service to explain the literature about "A moment of silence" and staff expectations should they wish to participate. Staff will also be introduced to the 4 A's should they wish to use this personal resource. Her use of an anonymous survey at the conclusion of the one-month implementation of "a moment of silence" is acceptable and will provide needed data about staff perceptions of the value of this project.

I understand this project does not have any direct impact on patient care or families, and will not require the collection of patient care data. Participation in this project will be completely voluntary and each member of the resuscitation team will have the option to opt out of participation at any time during the evidence based implementation project.

Sincerely,

[REDACTED]
Chief Nursing Officer

To: The California State University, Long Beach
Institutional Review Board

From: [REDACTED]

Re: Monique Velasco, MSN, RN
Doctor of Nursing Capstone Evidence Based Implementation Project

Ms. Velasco and I have met and discussed her proposed Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) evidence based implementation project to mitigate moral distress for resuscitation team healthcare providers. This project will implement two interventions. The first intervention is "The Pause" developed by Jonathon Bartels at the University of Virginia. It will be referred to as "A moment of silence" that will be conducted for 30 seconds at the end of unsuccessful cardiopulmonary resuscitations. The "moment of silence" will allow the resuscitation team to honor the life of the patient that has passed and to acknowledge the efforts of the team. The second intervention is the use of AACN's 4-A's debriefing tool to assist resuscitation staff members to identify and reduce moral distress associated with unsuccessful cardiopulmonary arrest events.

I agree with Ms. Velasco conducting a staff in service to explain the literature about "A moment of silence" and staff expectations should they wish to participate. Staff will also be introduced to the 4 A's should they wish to use this personal resource. Her use of an anonymous survey at the conclusion of the one-month implementation of "a moment of silence" is acceptable and will provide needed data about staff perceptions of the value of this project.

I understand this project does not have any direct impact on patient care or families, and will not require the collection of patient care data. Participation in this project will be completely voluntary and each member of the resuscitation team will have the option to opt out of participation at any time during the evidence based implementation project.

Sincerely,

[REDACTED]
Clinical Director – Critical Care Center

AMERICAN
ASSOCIATION
of CRITICAL-CARE
NURSES

July 12, 2017

Monique Velasco
11644 Glenworth Street
Santa Fe Springs, CA 90670

Dear Ms. Velasco:

Thank you for your reuse permission request. We hereby grant permission for your reuse of the AACN copyrighted content indicated below, free of charge, subject to the following conditions:

1. Suitable acknowledgment to the original source must be made, preferably as follows:
American Association of Critical-Care Nurses. *The 4 A's to Rise Above Moral Distress*.
Aliso Viejo, CA: American Association of Critical-Care Nurses. ©2004 by AACN. All rights reserved. Used with permission.
2. Content will be cited as a teaching guide and the diagram on page 2 will be used in full in a pamphlet, PowerPoint presentation, and addendum to a DNP project proposal. See item No. 1 for recommended citation. Full citation must accompany each mention.
3. This permission is granted for the following: individual academic use, United States, no foreign language translations. For other uses, such as future publication, please reapply.

Thank you for your interest in the American Association of Critical-Care Nurses.

Sincerely,

Michael Muscat
Publishing Manager

Accepted:

SIGNATURE

MSN, RN

TITLE

7/12/17

DATE

APPENDIX C

TEACHING PLAN

EDUCATION DEPARTMENT Critical Care Center

Mitigating Moral Distress for Resuscitation Team Healthcare Providers

COURSE DESCRIPTION:

This course will provide the Resuscitation Team Healthcare Providers with practical considerations focusing on the phenomenon of moral distress. The course will introduce two interventions to mitigate moral distress through peer collaboration and personal debriefing.

PREREQUISITE INCLUSION CRITERIA:

Health care providers who are members of the resuscitation team and ancillary services that provide supportive services to patients, families and staff during and after resuscitation events.

METHODS OF INSTRUCTION:

Power point Lecture
Pamphlet

METHOD OF EVALUATION:

Post implementation survey delivered via Qualtrics through staff email. All responses will remain anonymous and no personal identifiable data will be collected. Consent for participation in the survey will be included on the first page of the survey. Participants have the right to end participation in the survey at any time.

OBJECTIVES:

Describe the phenomenon of moral distress
Communicate the two interventions used to mitigate moral distress
Understand the significance of acknowledging the patient and the team
Recognize the importance of developing personal/professional coping strategies
Identify and care for personal and professional development

COURSE CONTENT:

1. Review the phenomenon of moral distress
 - a. In high intensity nursing units
 - b. Associated with end of life situations
 - c. May lead to emotional exhaustion
2. Introduce two interventions to mitigate moral distress
 - a. Moment of Silence – Developed by Jonathon Bartels (2014)
 - b. 4 A's to Mitigate Moral Distress - Developed by American Association of Critical Nurses (2004)
3. Emphasize the involvement in the interventions is completely voluntary. There is no obligation for participation in the project
4. Implementation of moment of silence at end of unsuccessful resuscitation events

5. Employee Assistance Resources available to all members of the hospital staff include an employee assistance program that offer anonymous counseling services

PILOT PROJECT – MOMENT OF SILENCE

PROTOCOL:

At the end of an unsuccessful resuscitation a lead member of the resuscitation team will institute a moment of silence. The team members will be informed that involvement in the moment of silence is completely voluntary and they can leave at any time. No notation will be made of who is present. There will be no gathering of data related to the moment of silence.

EVALUATION:

An online survey delivered via hospital email to all Resuscitation Team Healthcare Providers will be delivered after the completion of the pilot project. The survey will be completely anonymous. Consent for the survey will be included on the first page of the survey. Participation is completely voluntary. There is no obligation to participate in the survey.

COURSE COORDINATOR:

Monique Velasco, MSN, RN, CCRN

APPENDIX D

QUALTRICS SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Question 1: Consent of Project Participants

Participation in this survey is completely voluntary. Your answers will be analyzed with those of other people who complete this questionnaire; your responses will not be revealed, and will remain confidential. If you consent to voluntarily participate in this survey, please select "I agree" and the survey will open. You have the right to end participation in the survey at any time.

I Agree I Disagree

Question 2: Age

18-24 25-34 35-44 45-54 55-64 65-74 75 or more

Question 3: Gender

Male Female

Question 4: Ethnicity

American Indian or Alaskan Native Asian Black or African American

Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander White (Hispanic) White (Non-Hispanic)Other

Question 5: Education

Associates Bachelors Masters Doctorate Post-doctoral education

Question 6: Occupation

MD RN RT EMT Pharmacist Chaplain Social Worker

Question 7: Years of Experience

0-5 6-10 11-15 16-20 21-25 26-30 31 or more

For the next four questions please use the following scale to rate the extent that you felt:

Strongly Agree Agree Somewhat Agree Neither agree Nor disagree Somewhat Disagree Disagree Strongly Disagree

Question 8A: The education helped you to understand what moral distress is?

Question 8B: The moment of silence allowed you to personally acknowledge the patient?

Question 8C: The moment of silence allowed you to personally acknowledge the effort of the team?

Question 8D: The 4 A's helped you to acknowledge your own needs in handling moral distress?

Question 9: In the past month, how often were you a participant in an unsuccessful resuscitation event?

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 or more

Question 10: How often did you use the 4 A's as a debriefing process after a resuscitation?

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 or more

Question 11: How useful was the educational experience in assisting you to feel more comfortable in talking about moral distress with other healthcare providers?

Extremely useful Very useful Moderately useful Slightly useful Not at all useful

Question 12: For those who participated in a moment of silence, do you have any comments you wish to share about this personal experience, or suggestions you wish to share about the process.

Question 13: How valuable would you rate the moment of silence?

Excellent Good Average Poor Terrible

Question 14: Would you recommend continuing the moment of silence?

Definitely yes Probably yes Might or might not Probably not Definitely not

Question 15: Any comments?